

B.3 Storyboards by Camera-Equipped SHD Types

B.3.1 Driveway Camera Scenarios

Figure 4: **Driveway Camera – Route 1 (Tenant-initiated, Monetary Compensation, Accepted)**. Tenant Jane arrives at the Airbnb rental and expresses concerns that the driveway camera might invade her privacy. The host offers monetary compensation to address her concern, and Jane accepts.

Figure 5: **Driveway Camera – Route 2 (Tenant-initiated, Monetary Compensation, Declined)**. Tenant Jane arrives at the Airbnb rental and expresses concerns that the driveway camera might invade her privacy. The host offers monetary compensation to address her concern, but Jane declines.

Figure 6: **Driveway Camera – Route 3 (Tenant-initiated, Physical Adjustment, Accepted)**. Tenant Jane arrives at the Airbnb rental and expresses concerns that the driveway camera might invade her privacy. The host offers a physical adjustment by changing the camera's angle, and Jane accepts.

Jane is a privacy-conscious person. When she arrives at her Airbnb rental, she notices a smart camera installed in the driveway. She is concerned about her privacy being infringed by it.

Jane contacts the host and expresses her concerns about the camera. She wants it to be disabled during her stay for her privacy.

During the conversation, the host explains that the camera is installed for security purposes. As a compromise, the host proposes relocating the camera to only monitor the entrance for any suspicious individuals and/or activities.

Feeling uncomfortable and dissatisfied with the offer, Jane decides to leave the rental. As a penalty, she had to lose one day's rent.

Figure 7: Driveway Camera – Route 4 (Tenant-initiated, Physical Adjustment, Declined). Tenant Jane arrives at the Airbnb rental and expresses concerns that the driveway camera might invade her privacy. The host offers a physical adjustment by changing the camera's angle, but Jane declines.

Jane is a privacy-conscious person. When she arrives at her Airbnb rental, she notices a smart camera installed in the driveway. She is concerned about her privacy being infringed by it.

As soon as Jane checked-in, she receives a message from the Airbnb host, which included a list of privacy amenities in the property. This page also provided Jane with the option to contact the host if she had any questions.

During the conversation, the host explains that the camera is installed for security purposes. To compensate for Jane's lost in privacy, the host offers a partial refund.

Jane decides to accept the host's offer. This allows both Jane and the host to achieve their goals and find a mutually agreeable solution.

Figure 8: Driveway Camera – Route 5 (Host-initiated, Monetary Compensation, Accepted). The host proactively discloses the presence of the driveway camera when tenant Jane arrives. The host offers monetary compensation for any discomfort, and Jane accepts.

Jane is a privacy-conscious person. When she arrives at her Airbnb rental, she notices a smart camera installed in the driveway. She is concerned about her privacy being infringed by it.

As soon as Jane checked-in, she receives a message from the Airbnb host, which included a list of privacy amenities in the property. This page also provided Jane with the option to contact the host if she had any questions.

During the conversation, the host explains that the camera is installed for security purposes. To compensate for Jane's lost in privacy, the host offers a partial refund.

Feeling uncomfortable and dissatisfied with the offer, Jane decides to leave the rental. As a penalty, she had to lose one day's rent.

Figure 9: Driveway Camera – Route 6 (Host-initiated, Monetary Compensation, Declined). The host proactively discloses the presence of the driveway camera when tenant Jane arrives. The host offers monetary compensation for any discomfort, but Jane declines.

Figure 10: **Driveway Camera – Route 7 (Host-initiated, Physical Adjustment, Accepted)**. The host proactively discloses the presence of the driveway camera when tenant Jane arrives. The host offers a physical adjustment by changing the camera's angle, and Jane accepts.

Figure 11: **Driveway Camera – Route 8 (Host-initiated, Physical Adjustment, Declined)**. The host proactively discloses the presence of the driveway camera when tenant Jane arrives. The host offers a physical adjustment by changing the camera's angle, but Jane declines.

B.3.2 Video Conferencing Device for TVs Scenarios

Figure 12: **Smart TV – Route 1 (Tenant-initiated, Monetary Compensation, Accepted)**. Tenant Jane arrives at the Airbnb rental and expresses concerns that the camera on the Smart TV might invade her privacy. The host offers monetary compensation to address her concern, and Jane accepts.

Jane is a privacy-conscious person. Jane arrives at her Airbnb and finds a camera embedded in the smart TV in the living room. She is concerned that it might infringe her privacy during her stay.

Jane contacts the host and expresses her concerns about the camera embedded in the smart TV. She requests if the host can disable the camera to protect her privacy during her stay.

During the conversation, the host explains that the camera is used for video chat purposes. The host offers a partial refund to compensate Jane's loss of privacy so that she would feel more comfortable during her stay.

Feeling uncomfortable and dissatisfied with the offer, Jane decides to leave the rental. As a penalty, she had to lose one day's rent.

Figure 13: Smart TV – Route 2 (Tenant-initiated, Monetary Compensation, Declined). Tenant Jane arrives at the Airbnb rental and expresses concerns that the camera on the Smart TV might invade her privacy. The host offers monetary compensation to address her concern, but Jane declines.

Jane is a privacy-conscious person. Jane arrives at her Airbnb and finds a camera embedded in the smart TV in the living room. She is concerned that it might infringe her privacy during her stay.

Jane contacts the host and expresses her concerns about the camera embedded in the smart TV. She requests if the host can disable the camera to protect her privacy during her stay.

During the conversation, the host explains that the camera is used for video chat purposes. The host suggests Jane to cover the camera for her privacy so that she would feel more comfortable during her stay.

Jane thinks that covering the camera would adequately address her privacy concerns while still allowing the video chat features if needed.

Figure 14: Smart TV – Route 3 (Tenant-initiated, Physical Adjustment, Accepted). Tenant Jane arrives at the Airbnb rental and expresses concerns that the camera on the Smart TV might invade her privacy. The host offers a physical adjustment by covering the camera, and Jane accepts.

Jane is a privacy-conscious person. Jane arrives at her Airbnb and finds a camera embedded in the smart TV in the living room. She is concerned that it might infringe her privacy during her stay.

Jane contacts the host and expresses her concerns about the camera embedded in the smart TV. She requests if the host can disable the camera to protect her privacy during her stay.

During the conversation, the host explains that the camera is used for video chat purposes. The host suggests Jane to cover the camera for her privacy so that she would feel more comfortable during her stay.

Feeling uncomfortable and dissatisfied with the offer, Jane decides to leave the rental. As a penalty, she had to lose one day's rent.

Figure 15: Smart TV – Route 4 (Tenant-initiated, Physical Adjustment, Declined). Tenant Jane arrives at the Airbnb rental and expresses concerns that the camera on the Smart TV might invade her privacy. The host offers a physical adjustment by covering the camera, but Jane declines.

Jane is a privacy-conscious person. Jane arrives at her Airbnb and finds a camera embedded in the smart TV in the living room. She is concerned that it might infringe her privacy during her stay.

As soon as Jane checked-in, she receives a message from the Airbnb host, which included a list of privacy amenities in the property. This page also provided Jane with the option to contact the host if she had any questions.

During the conversation, the host explains that the camera is used for video chat purposes. The host offers a partial refund to compensate Jane's loss of privacy so that she would feel more comfortable during her stay.

Jane accepts the host's offer. This allows both Jane and the host to achieve their goals and find a mutually agreeable solution.

Figure 16: Smart TV – Route 5 (Host-initiated, Monetary Compensation, Accepted). The host proactively discloses the presence of the Smart TV camera when tenant Jane arrives. The host offers monetary compensation for any discomfort, and Jane accepts.

Jane is a privacy-conscious person. Jane arrives at her Airbnb and finds a camera embedded in the smart TV in the living room. She is concerned that it might infringe her privacy during her stay.

As soon as Jane checked-in, she receives a message from the Airbnb host, which included a list of privacy amenities in the property. This page also provided Jane with the option to contact the host if she had any questions.

During the conversation, the host explains that the camera is used for video chat purposes. The host suggests Jane to cover the camera for her privacy so that she would feel more comfortable during her stay.

Feeling uncomfortable and dissatisfied with the offer, Jane decides to leave the rental. As a penalty, she had to lose one day's rent.

Figure 17: Smart TV – Route 6 (Host-initiated, Monetary Compensation, Declined). The host proactively discloses the presence of the Smart TV camera when tenant Jane arrives. The host offers monetary compensation for any discomfort, but Jane declines.

Jane is a privacy-conscious person. Jane arrives at her Airbnb and finds a camera embedded in the smart TV in the living room. She is concerned that it might infringe her privacy during her stay.

As soon as Jane checked-in, she receives a message from the Airbnb host, which included a list of privacy amenities in the property. This page also provided Jane with the option to contact the host if she had any questions.

During the conversation, the host explains that the camera is used for video chat purposes. The host suggests Jane to cover the camera for her privacy so that she would feel more comfortable during her stay.

Jane thinks that covering the camera would adequately address her privacy concerns while still allowing the video chat features if needed.

Figure 18: Smart TV – Route 7 (Host-initiated, Physical Adjustment, Accepted). The host proactively discloses the presence of the Smart TV camera when tenant Jane arrives. The host offers a physical adjustment by covering the camera, and Jane accepts.

Jane is a privacy-conscious person. Jane arrives at her Airbnb and finds a camera embedded in the smart TV in the living room. She is concerned that it might infringe her privacy during her stay.

As soon as Jane checked-in, she receives a message from the Airbnb host, which included a list of privacy amenities in the property. This page also provided Jane with the option to contact the host if she had any questions.

During the conversation, the host explains that the camera is used for video chat purposes. The host suggests Jane to cover the camera for her privacy so that she would feel more comfortable during her stay.

Feeling uncomfortable and dissatisfied with the offer, Jane decides to leave the rental. As a penalty, she had to lose one day's rent.

Figure 19: **Smart TV – Route 8 (Host-initiated, Physical Adjustment, Declined)**. The host proactively discloses the presence of the Smart TV camera when tenant Jane arrives. The host offers a physical adjustment by covering the camera, but Jane declines.

B.3.3 Smart Display Device Scenarios

Jane is a privacy-conscious person. Jane arrives at her Airbnb and finds a smart speaker with embedded camera in the living room. She is concerned that it might infringe her privacy during her stay.

Jane contacts the host and expresses her concerns about the smart speaker with an embedded camera in the living room. She requests if the host can disable it to protect her privacy during her stay.

During the conversation, the host explains that the camera is used for video chat purposes. The host offers a partial refund to compensate Jane's privacy so that she would feel more comfortable during her stay.

Jane accepts the host's offer. This allows both Jane and the host to achieve their goals and find a mutually agreeable solution.

Figure 20: **Smart Speaker – Route 1 (Tenant-initiated, Monetary Compensation, Accepted)**. Tenant Jane arrives at the Airbnb rental and expresses concerns that the camera on the Smart Speaker might invade her privacy. The host offers monetary compensation to address her concern, and Jane accepts.

Jane is a privacy-conscious person. Jane arrives at her Airbnb and finds a smart speaker with embedded camera in the living room. She is concerned that it might infringe her privacy during her stay.

Jane contacts the host and expresses her concerns about the smart speaker with an embedded camera in the living room. She requests if the host can disable it to protect her privacy during her stay.

During the conversation, the host explains that the camera is used for video chat purposes. The host offers a partial refund to compensate Jane's privacy so that she would feel more comfortable during her stay.

Feeling uncomfortable and dissatisfied with the offer, Jane decides to leave the rental. As a penalty, she had to lose one day's rent.

Figure 21: **Smart Speaker – Route 2 (Tenant-initiated, Monetary Compensation, Declined)**. Tenant Jane arrives at the Airbnb rental and expresses concerns that the camera on the Smart Speaker might invade her privacy. The host offers monetary compensation to address her concern, but Jane declines.

Jane is a privacy-conscious person. Jane arrives at her Airbnb and finds a smart speaker with embedded camera in the living room. She is concerned that it might infringe her privacy during her stay.

Jane contacts the host and expresses her concerns about the smart speaker with an embedded camera in the living room. She requests if the host can disable it to protect her privacy during her stay.

During the conversation, the host explains that the camera is used for video chat purposes. The host suggests Jane to cover the smart speaker for her privacy so that she would feel more comfortable during her stay.

Jane thinks that covering the smart speaker would adequately address her privacy concerns and accepts the host's suggestion.

Figure 22: Smart Speaker – Route 3 (Tenant-initiated, Physical Adjustment, Accepted). Tenant Jane arrives at the Airbnb rental and expresses concerns that the camera on the Smart Speaker might invade her privacy. The host offers a physical adjustment by covering the camera, and Jane accepts.

Jane is a privacy-conscious person. Jane arrives at her Airbnb and finds a smart speaker with embedded camera in the living room. She is concerned that it might infringe her privacy during her stay.

Jane contacts the host and expresses her concerns about the smart speaker with an embedded camera in the living room. She requests if the host can disable it to protect her privacy during her stay.

During the conversation, the host explains that the camera is used for video chat purposes. The host suggests Jane to cover the smart speaker for her privacy so that she would feel more comfortable during her stay.

Feeling uncomfortable and dissatisfied with the offer, Jane decides to leave the rental. As a penalty, she had to lose one day's rent.

Figure 23: Smart Speaker – Route 4 (Tenant-initiated, Physical Adjustment, Declined). Tenant Jane arrives at the Airbnb rental and expresses concerns that the camera on the Smart Speaker might invade her privacy. The host offers a physical adjustment by covering the camera, but Jane declines.

Jane is a privacy-conscious person. Jane arrives at her Airbnb and finds a smart speaker with embedded camera in the living room. She is concerned that it might infringe her privacy during her stay.

As soon as Jane checked-in, she receives a message from the Airbnb host, which included a list of privacy amenities in the property. This page also provided Jane with the option to contact the host if she had any questions.

During the conversation, the host explains that the camera is used for video chat purposes. The host offers a partial refund to compensate Jane's privacy so that she would feel more comfortable during her stay.

Jane accepts the host's offer. This allows both Jane and the host to achieve their goals and find a mutually agreeable solution.

Figure 24: Smart Speaker – Route 5 (Host-initiated, Monetary Compensation, Accepted). The host proactively discloses the presence of the Smart Speaker camera when tenant Jane arrives. The host offers monetary compensation for any discomfort, and Jane accepts.

Jane is a privacy-conscious person. Jane arrives at her Airbnb and finds a smart speaker with embedded camera in the living room. She is concerned that it might infringe her privacy during her stay.

As soon as Jane checked-in, she receives a message from the Airbnb host, which included a list of privacy amenities in the property. This page also provided Jane with the option to contact the host if she had any questions.

During the conversation, the host explains that the camera is used for video chat purposes. The host offers a partial refund to compensate Jane's privacy so that she would feel more comfortable during her stay.

Feeling uncomfortable and dissatisfied with the offer, Jane decides to leave the rental. As a penalty, she had to lose one day's rent.

Figure 25: Smart Speaker – Route 6 (Host-initiated, Monetary Compensation, Declined). The host proactively discloses the presence of the Smart Speaker camera when tenant Jane arrives. The host offers monetary compensation for any discomfort, but Jane declines.

Jane is a privacy-conscious person. Jane arrives at her Airbnb and finds a smart speaker with embedded camera in the living room. She is concerned that it might infringe her privacy during her stay.

As soon as Jane checked-in, she receives a message from the Airbnb host, which included a list of privacy amenities in the property. This page also provided Jane with the option to contact the host if she had any questions.

During the conversation, the host explains that the camera is used for video chat purposes. The host suggests Jane to cover the smart speaker for her privacy so that she would feel more comfortable during her stay.

Jane thinks that covering the smart speaker would adequately address her privacy concerns and accepts the host's suggestion.

Figure 26: Smart Speaker – Route 7 (Host-initiated, Physical Adjustment, Accepted). The host proactively discloses the presence of the Smart Speaker camera when tenant Jane arrives. The host offers a physical adjustment by covering the camera, and Jane accepts.

Jane is a privacy-conscious person. Jane arrives at her Airbnb and finds a smart speaker with embedded camera in the living room. She is concerned that it might infringe her privacy during her stay.

As soon as Jane checked-in, she receives a message from the Airbnb host, which included a list of privacy amenities in the property. This page also provided Jane with the option to contact the host if she had any questions.

During the conversation, the host explains that the camera is used for video chat purposes. The host suggests Jane to cover the smart speaker for her privacy so that she would feel more comfortable during her stay.

Feeling uncomfortable and dissatisfied with the offer, Jane decides to leave the rental. As a penalty, she had to lose one day's rent.

Figure 27: Smart Speaker – Route 8 (Host-initiated, Physical Adjustment, Declined). The host proactively discloses the presence of the Smart Speaker camera when tenant Jane arrives. The host offers a physical adjustment by covering the camera, but Jane declines.